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**SARS-COV-2 INFECTION AND VIRULENCE:
COMPARISON BETWEEN INDIA AND UNITED STATES
OF AMERICA.**

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Abstract.

As of May 2021, the United States of America occupies the top position with respect to the total number of deaths of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2, developing COVID-19 and dying per 10000 population (or DPP-10000). India has recently (as of May 2021) registered an upsurge to the absolute number of deaths of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2, developing COVID-19 and dying. DPP-10000 Number for India also went considerably up from March 2021 to May 2021. However, in comparison to the high DPP-10000 Number registered in the United States of America, the IP-10000 Number and DPP-10000 Number for India remain comparatively low. Comparative study of DPP-10000 Number, and Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation during the periods of November 1, 2020 to February 28, 2021 and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 shows that high DPP-10000 Number during the months of November 1, 2020 to February 28, 2021 in the United States of America were associated with low Temperature and low Far Infrared Radiation while low IP-10000 Number and DPP-10000 Number during the months of March 1, 2020 to May 31, 2021 were associated with high Temperature and high Far Infrared Radiation. On the other hand, in India, the registered low DPP-10000 Number during the months of November

1, 2020 to February 28, 2021 was associated with high Humidity while the registered high DPP-10000 Number during the months of March 1, 2020 to May 31, 2021 were associated with low Humidity. The effects of Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation on SARS-COV-2 Infection and Virulence are well established, and need to be taken in consideration and fully investigated with respect to deaths due to SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 in India during the months of March 1, 2020 to May 31, 2021.

Introduction.

SARS-COV-2 and the diseases it causes [1-4] have differential effects in different countries. The United States of America occupies the top position with respect to the total number of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2 per 10000 population or IP-10000 and also the total number of deaths of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2, developing COVID-19 and dying or DPP-10000 [5,6]. India has recently (as of May 2021) registered an upsurge in the absolute total number of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2, developing and dying and total number of deaths of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2 and developing COVID-19 and dying per 10000 individuals (DPP-10000). The United States of America registered very high DPP-10000 Number during the months of November 2020, December 2020, January 2021 and February 2021 and relatively low DPP-10000 Number during the months of March 2021, April 2021 and May 2021 (See below). The opposite

occurred in India in which low DPP-10000 Number during the months of November 2020, December 2020, January 2021 and February 2021 and high DPP-10000 Number during the months of March 2021, April 2021 and May 2021 were registered. It is a truism that in the United States, the average Temperature and Far Infrared Radiation are low during the months of November 2020, December 2020, January 2021 and February 2021 and high during the months of March 2021, April 2021 and May 2021 (See below).

It was previously reported that there is a reverse correlation between SARS-COV-2 Infection and Virulence (or IP-10000 Number and DPP-10000 Number) and Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation [6-8]. Countries around the world were classified in various groups depending on the Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation that they experienced [8]. Group A countries included and Group countries included [8]. The recent increase in

the absolute total number of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2 and total number of deaths of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2, developing COVID-19 and dying in India is quite puzzling (See below) as it is the only country of Group countries to register such enormous increase. Many have argued that the incompetence of the Indian Government and its experts and pundits is the main cause of the high IP-10000 and DPP-10000 Numbers registered during the months of March, 2021, April 2021 and May 2021 [10] (See below). However, this is only partially correct because it does not explain why low DPP-10000 Number was registered during the months of November 2020, December 2020, January 2021 and February 2021 (See below). Here, it is shown that India registered significantly lower Humidity during the months of March, 2021, April 2021 and May 2021 than during the months of November 2020, December 2020, January 2021 and February 2021. The effect of Humidity on SARS-COV-2 Infection and Virulence is quite well established [7-9]. It is submitted that the low Humidity registered in India during the months of March, 2021, April 2021 and May 2021 is a major contributor to the high SARS-COV-2 Infection and associated deaths.

Methods.

Data for the total number of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2 and total number of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2, developing COVID-19 and dying for the United States and India were curated from the Department of Health of each country. DPP-10000 is defined as the total number of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2, developing COVID-19 and dying per 10000 population.

Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Irradiation values were curated from the Meteorological Readings and Forecasts of each country.

Data was analyzed for correlations by the Pearson method [12,13]. Differences between groups were determined by the student t-test [14,15] or One Way Anova test [15,16] with $p < 0.05$ accepted as statistically significant.

Results.

The total number of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2, developing COVID-19 and dying per 10000 population (DPP-10000 Number) for the United States America during the months of November 1 2020 to February 28 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May

31, 2021 were determined to be ~ 2.11 and ~ 0.81 respectively (Figure 1A). The DPP-10000 Numbers for India were determined to be during the months of November 1 2020 to February 28 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 were determined to be ~ 0.07 and 0.43 respectively (Figure B).

Figure 1. Significant Differences of DPP-10000 (Total Deaths of Individuals Infected with SARS-COV-2, Developing COVID-19 and Dying Per 10000 Population) between the months of November 1, 2020 to February 28, 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 in the United States of America (Panel A) and India (Panel B). (*p* values between Groups were less than 0.05).

Figure 2 shows DPP-10000 at different Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation during the months of November 1

2020 to February 28 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 in the United States of America. There were inverse correlations between DPP-10000 and Temperature and Far Infrared Radiation but not between DPP-10000 and Humidity (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Reverse correlation Between DPP-10000 and Temperature, $r = -0.78$ ($p < 0.05$) (Panel A) and Far Infrared Radiation, $r = -0.87$ ($p < 0.05$) (Panel B). No reverse correlation between DPP-10000 and Humidity, $r = -0.33$ ($p = 0.47$)

Figure 3 shows DPP-10000 at different Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation during the months of November 1 2020 to February 28 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 in India. There were no inverse correlations between DPP-10000 and Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation.

Figure 4 shows the difference in Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation during the months of November 1 2020 to February 28 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 in the United States. Figure 5 shows the difference in Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation during the months of November 1 2020 to February 28 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 in India. In India, the Temperature did not fluctuate much during the months of November 1 2020 to February 28 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 (~69° F v. ~83° F, from warm-to-warm Temperature) as it did in the United States of America (~52° F v. 61° F, from relatively cold to relatively warm Temperature). The Humidity in India also did not fluctuate much during the month of November 1 2020 to February 28 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 (~59 % v. ~48 %, from near dry to dry). There was also no much fluctuation in the level of

monthly Far Infrared Radiation (6.6×10^8 Joules/Km² v. 7.3×10^8 Joules/Km²) during the months of months of November 1 2020 to February 28 2021, and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021.

These results suggest that the high DPP-10000 Number registered in the United States during the months of November 1, 2020 to February 28, 2021 was associated with low average monthly Temperature ($\sim 52^{\circ}$ F), relatively average monthly Humidity ($\sim 69\%$) and low average monthly Far Infrared Radiation (4.28×10^8 Joules/Km²) and the low DPP-10000 Number registered in the United States during the months of March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 are associated with relatively high average monthly Temperature ($\sim 61^{\circ}$ F), relatively average monthly humidity ($\sim 67\%$) and relatively average monthly Far Infrared Radiation (7.19×10^8 Joules/Km²) (Figure 4). In India, the low DPP-10000 Number registered during the months of November 1, 2020 to February 28, 2021 was associated with relatively high average monthly Temperature (69° F), relatively high average Humidity ($\sim 59\%$) and relatively average monthly Far Infrared Radiation (6.73×10^8 Joules/Km²). The relatively high DPP-10000 Number registered in India during the months of March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 was associated with high average monthly Temperature ($\sim 83^{\circ}$ F) relatively low Humidity ($\sim 48\%$) and relatively average monthly Far Infrared Radiation (7.56×10^8 Joules/Km²). It therefore appears that the

relative low Humidity ($\sim 48\%$) experienced by India during the months of of March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 could explain the relatively high DPP-10000 registered in India during the months of of March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021.

Discussion.

The results described in this paper confirms the previous suggestions that DPP-10000 Number (or the total number of individuals infected with SARS-COV-2, developing

COVID-19 and dying per 10000 population) which is a measure of Virulence of SARS-COV-2 is inversely correlated with Temperature and Far Infrared radiation in the United States of America [7,17]. Thus, during the months November 1, 2020 to February 28, 2021, when the Temperature and Far Infrared Radiation were relatively low, the United States of America experienced high DPP-10000 Number while during the months of March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 when the Temperature and Far Infrared Radiation were relatively high, the the United States of America experienced low DPP-10000 Number. In India, the Temperature and the Far Infrared Radiation did not fluctuate much during the months of November 1, 2020 to February 28, 2021 and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021. However, there was much fluctuation in the level of Humidity during the months of November 1, 2020 to February 28, 2021 and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021. It is submitted that the change in Humidity in India during the months of November 1, 2020 to February 28, 2021 and March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 can account for the upsurge of DPP-10000 registered in India during the months of March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021. However, it does not absolve the Government of India and its experts and pundits from the failure to

mount an effective response to the upsurge of DPP-10000 registered during the months of March 1, 2021 to May 31, 2021 as observed in other countries where Humidity is an important factor in SARS-COV-2 Infectivity and Virulence [7-9].

The effects of Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation on the Infectivity and Virulence of viruses that infect humans are fairly well established [7-9,17]. It is not clear why these scientific facts have not been exploited to combat SARS-COV-2 Infection and Virulence. As the DPP-10000 Numbers plummet in summer in most Group countries, a few countries, including India where Humidity is an important factor in SARS-COV-2 Infection and Virulence are experiencing significant increases in DPP-10000. The current strategies to combat SARS-COV-2 and COVID-19 are through vaccinations with various unproven vaccines to achieve the proverbial "Herd Immunity"/. Students of the Art of War know that putting all the eggs in one basket is not only foolhardy but also quite dangerous. It is submitted that the low DPP-10000 Numbers observed in many countries are not due to the effects of vaccines but to the effects of high Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation. It is submitted that one should

review several key papers that describe the effects of Temperature, Humidity and Far Infrared Radiation on the infectivity and virulence of viruses that infect humans [7-9,17,31]. That SARS-COV-2 attacks seasonally must be investigated in full and appropriate countermeasures based on that knowledge must be applied. There are already procedures that can be implemented to prevent SARS-COV-2 Infection and Virulence during the cold season which is just around the corner in a couple of months.

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